

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF STATE POLICY REGARDING YOUTH IN DIAGNOSTIC ASSESSMENT OF THE EDUCATION LEVEL OF TEENAGE STUDENTS

Mamatkulova Ozoda

**Doctoral student of the scientific research institute of pedagogical
sciences of Uzbekistan named after TN Kori Niyoz**

Abstract: In this article, the importance of the state policy on youth in the diagnostic assessment of the educational level of adolescent students is described, as well as relevant conclusions are drawn on this topic.

Key words: youth, state, youth policy, reform, knowledge, education, training, openness, transparency, right, freedom, morality, opportunity.

In our country young people issue from the first years of our independence priority from issues one is considered Because young people of the country support and trust . That's it because of of independence initial since years to young people about state policy basics work released To young people about state policy this state by done to be increased and young people social in terms of formation and their intellectual , creative and another direction potential maturity find for conditions to be created mean holding socio-economic , organizational and legal measures system ¹.

To young people about state of politics main principles of the following consists of :

- openness and transparency ;
- to young people about state policy to the left in release of young people participation reach
- young people initiatives support and encourage ;
- spiritual , moral and cultural of values priority ;
- of young people to be humiliated road not to be placed .

Uzbekistan on November 20 , 1991 Republic of acceptance made " Uzbekistan in the Republic to young people about state policy basics on " in Article 1 of Law No. 429-XII to young people about state of politics the goal and duties set given

¹ " On State Policy Regarding Youth " . September 14, 2016. O'RQ-No. 406// People's word. September 15, 2016.

To young people about politics Uzbekistan Republic state of activity priority direction being his purpose of young people social formation and maturity find , creative talent society interests road in opportunity as long as full come true output for socio - economic , legal , organizational in terms of conditions Create and them from guaranteeing consists of

Uzbekistan in the Republic to young people about state policy the following to the rules based on :

- nationality , race , language, religion , social position , gender, education and political from faith strictly look young people about care to do
- young people legal and social in terms of protection to do
- national cultural of tradition from generation to generation the transition of generations spiritual connection ;
- of young people initiatives support ,
- young people Uzbekistan Republic Constitution and laws within own realization of interests road the free choose to get guarantee to give
- society development , especially the republic young people to his life about politics and programs work exit and done in raising of young people directly participation reach
- the right and of duties freedom and citizenship responsibility unit

To young people about state of politics the goal and task now brought up going of young people the world politics to the stage own rights good understood without our country developed countries to the line enter to get directed . Any society development road from without deviating advance that he went sari this development providing to him new strength and power giving , modern thinking , har bilaterally knowledgeable and smart young to personnel demand that is and the need is constant increased keeps going Today's in the day in our country done being increased to young people attention and of care organic continue is doing when you see it politics that's what it 's all about the truth every bilaterally deep understand , far away looking forward to the work conduct principle incarnate that it is trust harvest we do

this regard of work continuation died on February 7 , 2017 Uzbekistan Republic of President Sh. Mirziyoyev by acceptance made " Uzbekistan Republic more development according to Actions strategy on" in paragraph 4 of Decree No. PF-4947 " in 2017-2021 Uzbekistan Republic development five priority direction

according to Actions strategy " People with communication and a person interests in the year done to increase The State program was approved ².

This is it In 2017-2021 , according to paragraph 1 of the decree Uzbekistan Republic development five priority direction according to Actions strategy confirmed . Physically healthy , mentally and mentally developed , independent thinking , to the Motherland loyal , firm vital point of view look have young people education , democratic reforms deepening and citizenship society development in the process their social activity increase , medium special , profession and higher education institutions graduates to work placing and private entrepreneurship to the field attraction age , age generation creative and intellectual potential support and come true release , kids and young people in the middle healthy marriage style form them physical education and to sports wide attraction reach , young people social protection do , young families for worthy housing and social and household conditions to create , to young people about state policy done in raising state authority and management bodies , education institutions , youth and another of organizations efficient activities organize in 2017-2021 Uzbekistan Republic development five priority direction according to Actions in the strategy " To the youth about state policy called " improvement ". reflected in a separate item (item 4.5). was made and social the field development five priority from directions one's in the composition own expression found. This in clause to young people about state policy to improve directed the following tasks marked :

- physically healthy , mentally and mentally developed , independent thinking , to the Motherland faithful, firm vital point of view look have young people education , democratic reforms deepening and citizenship society development in the process their social activity increase

- medium special , profession and higher education institutions graduates to work placing and private entrepreneurship to the field attraction reach

- young generation creative and intellectual potential support and come true release , kids and young people in the middle healthy marriage style form them physical education and to sports wide attraction reach

²Scientific-methodological brochure on the study of the State program on the implementation of the strategy of actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the "Year of communication with the people and human interests" in 2017-2021 / University of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Secondary Special Education, Tashkent State University of Economics. - T.: "Spirituality" publishing house, 2017. -244 pages.

- young people social protection do , young families for worthy housing and social and household conditions Create ;

- to young people about state policy done in raising state authority and management bodies , education institutions , youth and another of organizations efficient activities organize to achieve³

Uzbekistan President Sh. Mirziyoyev initiative with " People with communication and a person interests to young people in 2017, which was called " year ". about state policy improvement about serious affairs completion - 25 assignments execution sure by doing set it was put . It is known that on September 14, 2016 , Uzbekistan 33 articles of the Republic consists of " To the youth about state policy about". Law acceptance done . This is it of the law acceptance to be done relationship with Uzbekistan Adopted on November 20, 1991 made " Uzbekistan in the Republic to young people about state of politics basics on" Law No. 429-XII own strength lost

This is it of the law acceptance to be done very big important have it has been . Including our country In his Address to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 22, 2017, the President said the following: "We are young generation every bilaterally healthy and perfect reached bring up regarding our work new to stage raise in order to " To the youth about state policy about". the law new in editing acceptance we did On this basis new approaches to life active current is ⁴being done .

This law provides young people with great opportunities to receive modern education, purchase and construction of housing, and get preferential loans for starting a family, as well as systematic social guarantees. In conclusion, the development of the state policy on youth and its improvement has become of great practical importance in ensuring the rights and freedoms of young people and creating conditions for their development.

In conclusion, the foundations of the State Policy on Youth have been developed and widely implemented in Uzbekistan. As a result of the implementation of the state policy on youth, young people who are instilled in the thinking of the national idea and who are the successors of the tomorrow of our country have been formed . Today's youth is ideologically, scientifically, politically and culturally

³Uzbekistan Republic " Uzbekistan Republic more development according to Actions strategy on" Decree PF-4947. February 7, 2017. T.: "Justice". 2017. 112 pages .

⁴The speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his Address to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 22, 2017// Xalq sozi, December 23, 2017.

different from the youth formed in the pre-independence period. The reason for this is that after we gained our independence, young people are concerned about the fate of their country, they are proud of their achievements in various cultural and educational events, sports competitions and games, and they honor their motherland. , feelings of joy and confidence in the future were formed.

Spiritual poverty among young people is determined primarily by the fact that material support has become a vital criterion, placing material needs at a high level, indolence, lack of courage, and a low level of political consciousness. We need to understand how important it is to take them out of their spiritual poverty and to inculcate in them such qualities as knowledge and enlightenment, happiness, patriotism, determination.

From the above, we can see that in our country, great attention is paid to youth. Therefore, we, the youth, should also be worthy children and contribute to the development of our country. Because the peace and well-being of our rapidly developing Uzbekistan is in the hands of the youth, who are the owners of the future. If we, the modern generation, grow up to be perfect and mature, if we consistently build honor and national pride in ourselves, our Motherland will become such a powerful country. Indeed, it is the honorable duty of every person living in our heavenly Uzbekistan to reliably protect our homeland, the peace and tranquility of our people, to be a patriot, to live with feelings of loyalty and self-sacrifice!

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